

С.Насриддинова

Андижанский государственный медицинский институт

Н.А.Насирдинова

Андижанский государственный медицинский институт

ОСОБЕННОСТИ КЛИНИЧЕСКОГО ТЕЧЕНИЯ НЕОНАТАЛЬНЫХ СУДОРОГ

S. Nasriddinova

Andijan State Medical Institute

N.A. Nasirdinova

Andijan State Medical Institute

FEATURES OF THE CLINICAL COURSE OF NEONATAL CAPS

Annotation. Perinatal pathology of the nervous system includes: hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy due to brain damage during fetal development or delivery (except for traumatic brain damage), impaired blood supply to the brain, oxygen starvation or exposure to toxins; convulsive syndrome - uncontrolled paroxysmal muscle contractions caused by brain damage, infections, toxins, metabolic diseases, etc.; intracranial bleeding - birth trauma, long-term oxygen starvation, intrauterine infections, subdural hemorrhages, epidural hemorrhages, subarachnoid hemorrhages as a result of blood coagulation disorders.

Key words. Lesion, flatulence, syndromes, fontanel, hydrocephalus, epilepsy, hyperactive, cerebroasthenic syndrome.

Introduction. The problem of predicting the outcomes of NS is one of the most complex and fundamentally important in pediatrics and neurology. Many authors point to adverse outcomes of NS. The recommendations of the ILAE Classification

and Terminology Commission (Berg A.T. et al., 2010) define three electroclinical epileptic syndromes of the neonatal period, characterized by a regulated onset age, course and prognosis features: benign familial neonatal epilepsy, early myoclonic encephalopathy, syndrome Otahara (early infantile epileptic encephalopathy with suppressive-explosive changes on the EEG) (Khaletskaya, O.V. et al., 2003). The prognosis for the first form is favorable, while the last two diseases are classified as epileptic encephalopathies of neonatal and infancy with extremely unfavorable outcomes.

Children with NS have a risk of developing cerebral palsy (CP) that is 55-70 times higher than that of children who did not suffer from NS, the risk of developing epilepsy is 18 times, the risk of neuropsychic developmental delay (NPD) is 5.3 times higher, than in the general population. With NS, the risk of developing resistant forms of epilepsy and disorders of neuropsychic development increases. Therefore, NS should be included in the high-risk group for neurodevelopmental disorders and epilepsy.

Given the above, we set a goal: to study the features of the course of neonatal seizures in full-term newborns and to determine the ways of correction to reduce the risk of possible severe neurological complications.

Material and methods of the study: The study is based on examination data of 30 children with neonatal convulsions aged from birth to 28 days (neonatal period). The surveyed were divided into 2 age groups: 0-15 days from birth - 24 newborns (80%) and 15-28 days from birth - 6 children (20%). The average age of children was 9.9 ± 0.3 days from birth. All patients underwent clinical-neurological, neurosonographic and clinical-laboratory research methods.

Results of the study: In order to identify the causes leading to the development of neonatal convulsions, mothers' diseases suffered during pregnancy were studied. Studies have shown that NS was more often manifested in mothers who had such diseases as pyelonephritis (61.9%), iron deficiency anemia (84.1%) and severe

stressful situations (49.2%) during pregnancy. A neurosonographic study showed that most of the examined children had hypoxic-ischemic disorders, expansion of the subarachnoid space and lateral ventricles, and a significant increase in intracranial pressure. Assessment of the neurological status was carried out both at the first appearance of neonatal seizures, and in dynamics during the year, taking into account the neuropsychological status. Studies have shown the presence at the beginning of the disease of increased muscle tone (72.4%), revitalization of tendon reflexes (88.2%), general hyperesthesia (55.1%), phonophobia (37.9%). Subsequently, neurological disorders progressed in these children, a lag in psychomotor development developed (74.8%), transformation into epileptic seizures (38.3%), and difficulties in consolidating skills (81.6%).

Conclusions: The severity of neonatal seizures depends on the number of maternal risk factors during pregnancy. The maximum frequency of resistant and recurrent episodes of neonatal seizures (64.3%) was found in the group with three risk factors. Neonatal convulsions in perinatal lesions of the nervous system lead to an increase in the frequency of neurological disorders in children. In 79.4% of cases, children who have undergone neonatal convulsions have neurological disorders: neuropsychiatric retardation, epilepsy and convulsive conditions, which negatively affects the overall development of such children.

REFERENCES:

1. Majidov N. M. "General Neurology". Tashkent, 1995.
2. Shomansurov Sh.Sh. "Nervous and mental diseases". Tashkent, 1995.
3. Aslanov A. M. "Nervous diseases" Tashkent, 1998.
4. Murtalibov Sh. A. "Reference from Psychiatry" Tashkent, 1993.
5. Shomansurov Sh.Sh. "Children's nervous diseases" Tashkent, 1995.